

Sub Nanometer Clusters in Catalysis

Estefanía Fernández and Mercedes Boronat *

Instituto de Tecnología Química (UPV-CSIC), Universitat Politècnica de València –
Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas, Avda. de los Naranjos s/n, 46022
Valencia, Spain.

E-mail: boronat@itq.upv.es

Abstract

Sub nanometer transition metal clusters composed by a small number of atoms exhibit unexpected electronic, optical, magnetic and catalytic properties that often change substantially as a function of cluster atomicity. Several factors influence their unique catalytic behavior, including their discrete electronic structure of molecular-like orbitals and the accessibility of their low-coordinated atoms. In addition, these factors are strongly correlated so that changes in their morphology may provoke large modifications to their electronic structure and vice versa. The thermodynamic instability of clusters makes necessary to stabilize them with protective ligands in solution or to support them on solid matrices for practical applications, which introduces non-negligible modifications into their properties. Understanding their cause and extent is the key point to potentially achieve a fine tuning of their catalytic behavior. Selected examples are discussed illustrating important points on this matter, such as the influence of cluster morphology on reactivity, the need of anchoring clusters to avoid sintering and deactivation, and the possible formation of clusters in solution or under reaction conditions, with the associated difficulty to identify them as the true active species.

Keywords: Metal clusters, active species, electronic structure, metal-support interaction, reaction mechanism

1. Introduction

Bridging the gap between transition metal organometallic complexes with well-defined isolated active centers and heterogeneous catalysts based on metal nanoparticles with diameter between 1 and 10 nm as the active phase, sub nanometer transition metal clusters have emerged in the last decades as a new regime where unexpected catalytic properties and applications are being reported regularly. [1-8] Among the several factors influencing the unique catalytic behavior of metal clusters composed by a small number of atoms, namely less than ~ 50 atoms, the most important are their electronic structure consisting of discrete levels and localized molecular orbitals similar to those present in molecules, and the low coordination and accessibility to reactant molecules of all atoms in the cluster. [9-10]

The under-coordination and electronic accessibility of the metal atoms in clusters makes them highly reactive and thermodynamically unstable, so that it becomes necessary to protect them with stabilizing ligands and to support them on solid organic or inorganic matrices for practical catalytic applications. Their intrinsic instability poses a challenge for the synthesis of atomically precise clusters, which adds to the difficulties associated to their subsequent anchoring on the solid support, the removal of the stabilizing ligand and the possible sintering of the clusters into larger particles.

Recent advances in synthesis procedures and characterization techniques have allowed to prepare atomically-precise materials, whose study by means of spectroscopic and microscopic techniques combined with kinetic and computational investigations, is leading to an unprecedented progress in the understanding of the catalytic behavior of sub nanometer metal clusters. [4-9, 11] It is established that the interaction of the metal cluster with the organic or inorganic support modifies, to a greater or lesser extent, the geometry, electronic structure, charge state and, being all of them strongly correlated, the catalytic properties of the supported cluster. [12-13] The key point in the design and application of subnanometer clusters to catalysis is to understand how the electronic and catalytic properties of the metal clusters are modified by the interaction with the support, and take advantage of this knowledge to control and finely tune their catalytic behavior.

The study of supported clusters is, at this moment, one of the most promising, wide and prolific research lines in heterogeneous catalysis. In this contribution we intend to summarize the foundations behind the differential properties of sub nanometer clusters,

to review recent work devoted to investigate their electronic and geometric properties using both theoretical and experimental methods, and to correlate these properties with their catalytic activity. The subject matter is nevertheless broad and there are several review articles that the reader is encouraged to consult to expand on the different aspects. [1-14 POTSER ACĭ]

2. Electronic Structure of Metal Clusters

When the size of metal clusters becomes comparable to the Fermi wavelength, $\lambda_F < 1$ nm, that is, in the sub nanometer regime, quantum confinement effects produce a discrete distribution of electronic states with a non-zero HOMO-LUMO gap. The electrons in sub nanometer clusters are not fully delocalized as in the bulk metal, and therefore clusters can be considered non-metallic. [10, 11] The behavior of clusters consequently depends on geometric, electronic and size-dependent properties that are closely interrelated.

The geometries of transition metal clusters are dominated by their partially filled (fully filled in the case of noble metals) *d* shell, that favors compact structures as a way to maximize the interaction between the rather localized *d* orbitals, and by the hybridization of the *ns*-(*n*-1)*d* orbitals induced by the relativistic contraction of the inner *s* and *p* shells, that favors planar structures and is stronger in heavier atoms like Pt and Au. [10, 15, 16] As a consequence of these effects being produced to a different extent for each element, the size-limit for the 2D to 3D transition differs from one metal to another. Thus, while the most stable isomers of Ni₄ and Pd₄ are tetrahedral, [17,18] planar structures are the most stable configurations of Cu, Ag and Pt clusters composed by up to 6 atoms, [19, 20, 21] and Au₈ is the smallest gold cluster with a 3D structure. [22, 23] In general, there are often several low-lying isomers with only slightly different stability, especially as the cluster size increases. We recently investigated the equilibrium geometries of the most stable isomers of Cu_{*n*} clusters with $3 \leq n \leq 8$ using different levels of calculation and found, in agreement with previous work, that 2D structures are the most stable up to *n* = 6 (see Figure 1a). [20] At the highest computational level considered in that study, B3PW91/6-311+G(d,p), the difference in energy between the 2D and 3D isomers of Cu₄, Cu₅ and Cu₆ clusters is around 7-8 kcal/mol. As cluster atomicity increases, the most stable isomers are always 3D, and the difference in stability between them is reduced. In this sense, the co-existence of the two lowest energy isomers of Cu₈ obtained from the theoretical study

is supported by experimental results from Lecoultre et al., who showed that both isomers contribute to the measured UV-visible absorption spectra of Cu_8 clusters in Ne. [24]

Figure 1. Geometric and electronic properties of Cu_n clusters with $3 \leq n \leq 8$. a) Relative stability of isomers for each atomicity and b) calculated isosurfaces and energy levels of the lowest unoccupied (LUMO) and highest occupied (HOMO) orbitals, calculated at the B3PW91/6-311+G(d,p) level using the Gaussian09 program. The arrows indicate the HOMO-LUMO gap for each cluster. Adapted with permission from [20]. Copyright 2015 American Chemical Society. Notice that the second most stable isomer of Cu_6 is not absolutely planar, but since it is composed by one unique layer of atoms cannot be strictly considered 3D.

The possible co-existence of different isomers close in energy is relevant, because the geometric and electronic structures of metal clusters are intimately correlated. The frontier orbitals (HOMO and LUMO) of small clusters usually consist of several lobes localized on the low coordinated metal atoms and fully accessible to interaction with reactant molecules. The shape and energy level of these orbitals depend not only on the

atomicity of the metal cluster, but also on its morphology (see Figure 1b). For instance, the HOMO and LUMO orbitals of the most stable Cu_5 isomer are localized at the edges of the planar structure, and therefore no molecular adsorption nor reactivity is in principle expected on the face of the cluster. In the 3D Cu_5 cluster, however, a large contribution to the frontier orbitals is found in the triangular facets. In a similar way, the frontier orbitals of the 2D Cu_6 isomer are mainly localized at the corner atoms of the triangle, while in the 3D structure large orbital lobes are observed above the plane formed by the four atoms in a rhombus-type arrangement. In both cases, the HOMO-LUMO energy gap for the 3D cluster is moreover clearly reduced as compared to that of the 2D isomer (see Figure 1b).

As the number of atoms in the cluster increases and 3D structures are favored, more metal-metal bonds are formed, the surface atoms are more coordinated, and the contribution of the atoms inside the cluster to the composition of the frontier orbitals becomes more important, with a concomitant loss in the capability of orbital overlap with interacting molecules. In addition, as the atomicity increases the electronic distribution of clusters tends to the band structure of the bulk metal, as exemplified in Figure 2 where the HOMO-LUMO gap of Ag_n clusters converges to the Fermi level of the bulk crystal and the main features of the bulk density of states are already present in clusters composed by 75 atoms. [21]

Figure 2. Electronic structure for the most stable isomers of Ag_n ($1 < n < 75$) clusters and silver bulk calculated at the DFT level. The red lines indicate the electronic energy levels. Up spin states (left) and down spin states (right) are separated by a thin vertical black line for spin-polarized systems. The space between HOMO and LUMO is indicated in blue.

Each projected value of s, p, and d to the Kohn–Sham state is connected by light blue, green, and dark blue lines, respectively. The Fermi level of silver bulk is represented in its DOS by a dashed line. Adapted with permission from [21]. Copyright 2009 AIP Publishing.

The change in the electronic structure of particles as the size decreases from the bulk metal is reflected in their optical properties (Figure 3). [5, 25] Thus, larger metal nanoparticles present the so-called surface plasmon absorption bands under UV-visible radiation, produced from the resonance between the irradiating light and the oscillation of the electrons confined in their conduction band. [26-28] This resonance is strongest and shifted to the visible part of the electromagnetic spectrum for the noble metals (Cu, Ag, Au) due to the higher polarizability of their electrons, which provides them of characteristic colors and also gives rise to a sharper bandwidth compared to other transition metals. [26] In contrast, UV-visible absorption spectra of clusters are more similar to those of molecules, presenting thin peaks arising from the discretization of their electronic structure. In addition, the absorbed radiation is similarly emitted in the form of a transition, causing fluorescence (see Figure 3). [27-29] Clusters hence behave like semiconductors, and while the surface plasmon of NPs changes mainly due to their shape, the UV-visible absorption spectra and the fluorescence emission wavelength of clusters changes severely with cluster size. [27] It is precisely due to this strong size-dependence that UV-visible and photoluminescence spectra are commonly employed to characterize the size of cluster samples. The atomicity is approximately obtained from the band gap of the cluster by applying a simple equation from a jellium model, [30] and the band gap is at the same time obtained either from a Tauc plot of the UV-visible absorption spectra or from the emission wavelength of photoluminescent spectra. [31] In the jellium model, the valence electrons are assumed to be delocalized and moving in the potential that the nuclei and core electrons produce, which are approximated to a uniform background of positive charge. [30] The model also provides a relatively simple explanation to the so-called magic numbers for transition metal clusters, which indicate cluster sizes that show larger HOMO-LUMO gaps and a greater stability than the rest [32-34]. These extra-stable structures are achieved when a determined number of electrons is reached in the system and a closed-shell electronic configuration, a complete jellium level, is produced.

Figure 3. a) Schematic representation of photoluminescence properties of copper particles with size. Small clusters show fluorescence, contrary to intermediate and large clusters. Estimated absorption wavelengths for each cluster are shown. Adapted from ref. [25]. B) (Up) Possible structures of ligand-stabilized gold clusters of increasing size: AuNC@PEI, AuNC@MUA and AuNC@DHLA. (Down) From left to right (blue to red), photographs of the corresponding fluorescent gold nanoclusters made in PEI, MUA or DHLA under white light and excited with a UV lamp. Adapted from ref. [5].

In a similar way, the s^1 electronic configuration of the three coinage metals (Cu, Ag and Au), albeit modified by the sd hybridization, produces stable closed-shell electronic configurations for even clusters, leading to a characteristic even-odd trend with size for certain properties like the HOMO-LUMO energy gap, the electron detachment energy or the ionization potential. [19, 21-23] The existence of an odd-even alternation in the HOMO-LUMO gap for Ag_n clusters containing up to ~ 40 atoms, that is, with particle diameter of ~ 1 nm, is clearly observed in Figure 2. This behavior was also clearly

evidenced in a comparative study of neutral, anionic and cationic Cu_n and Pt_n clusters with $2 \leq n \leq 14$ by Chaves et al. [19]. For example, the total magnetic moment of neutral Cu_n clusters oscillates between $0 \mu_B$ and $1 \mu_B$ for even and odd number of atoms, respectively, which can be explained by the $3d^{10}4s^1$ electronic configuration of Cu that results in an unpaired electron in clusters with an odd number of atoms. Accordingly, the trend for cationic Cu_n^+ and anionic Cu_n^- clusters is the opposite. The total magnetic moment of Pt_n clusters, in contrast, does not show any oscillatory trend, because it is due to the partial occupation of the 5d states (Figure 4a). A similar oscillatory or zig-zag-like behavior was observed for the HOMO-LUMO energy gap, detachment energy and ionization potential of Cu_n clusters, but not for Pt_n clusters (Figure 4b).

The strong interplay between electronic structure and geometry also explains the dramatic change in the shape of metal clusters with charge observed for some systems. Thus, the preferred triangular geometry obtained for neutral Pt_3 , Cu_3 , and Au_3 clusters turns into linear structures for anionic Pt_3^- , Cu_3^- , and Au_3^- clusters (see Figure 4c). The distorted rhombus geometry preferred for neutral Pt_4 changes to a planar square upon addition of one electron forming Pt_4^- , and to a tetrahedron upon removal of one electron generating cationic Pt_4^+ . And while 3D structures are also obtained for cationic Cu_5^+ and Pt_5^+ , the corresponding neutral Cu_5 and Pt_5 and anionic Cu_5^- and Pt_5^- are 2D. As regards gold, the global minimum for neutral Au_4 cluster is a rhombus, and two different degenerate structures were obtained by Häkkinen and Landman for anionic Au_4^- clusters, a Y-shaped geometry (similar to that depicted in Figure 1 for Cu_4), and a linear zig-zag structure, both different from rhombus that is the global minimum for the neutral Au_4 cluster.[22] DFT calculations proposed a rhombus geometry for the most stable isomers of Au_4^+ and Ag_4^+ clusters, which was experimentally confirmed by photodissociation spectroscopy [35] As explained before for neutral clusters, the relativistic *sd* hybridization is enhanced for the heavier elements, and the anionic Pt_n^- and Au_n^- also tend to be planar up to sizes larger than those found for other elements. [19, 36]

Figure 4. Geometric and electronic properties of neutral, cationic and anionic Cu_n and Pt_n clusters. a) Total magnetic moment (mT) and b) HOMO-LUMO energy gap (E_g) as a function of cluster atomicity for neutral (red circles), cationic (black squares) and anionic (blue triangles) Cu_n (empty symbols) and Pt_n (filled symbols) clusters. c) Most stable isomer for each atomicity obtained at the DFT-PBE level. Adapted with permission from [19]. Copyright 2014 American Chemical Society.

Even-odd trends are also sometimes reflected in the interaction of neutral and charged clusters with molecules. Early experiments detected a pattern in the adsorption of O₂ to negatively charged small gold clusters, where only anionic clusters with an even number of atoms, and therefore an odd number of valence electrons, showed significant O₂ uptake. [37, 38] A systematic density functional theory investigation of the molecular and dissociative adsorption of O₂ on neutral and anionic Au_n clusters with 2 ≤ n ≤ 8 [39] confirmed this trend. Molecular O₂ adsorption was found stronger on anionic clusters than on neutral ones (see Figure 5a), and in both systems binding energies exhibited odd-even oscillations, with the calculated E_b values being larger for clusters with an odd number of electrons, that is, with an open electron-shell structure. Molecular adsorption was accompanied by a lengthening of the O-O bond due to charge transfer to one of the empty antibonding 2π* orbitals of O₂. Dissociative adsorption was found energetically favored on clusters composed by at least four atoms, and was always accompanied by large changes in the geometrical structure of the metal cluster.

The interaction of molecular O₂ with isolated gold, silver and copper clusters and nanoparticles has been theoretically investigated in our group, and it has been found that not only particle size but also particle morphology are key parameters controlling the activation and dissociation of O₂. [20, 40, 41-43] Several different types of complexes can be formed upon adsorption of molecular O₂ on metal clusters and nanoparticles depending on the coordination and nature of the metal atoms (Figure 5b). In the case of small planar clusters, and taking into account the shape of the cluster orbitals discussed before, O₂ adsorbs preferentially at corners and edges, forming either *mono*-coordinated complexes in which only one bond is formed between a O atom and a low-coordinated metal atom, or bi-coordinated complexes with the two O atoms directly attached to the same metal atom (*top* mode) or with each of the two O atoms in the molecule coordinated to a different metal atom (*bridge* mode). In 3D clusters and nanoparticles, molecular O₂ can also adsorb at hollow positions on the (111) and (100) facets, and in these cases one or the two O atoms are directly attached to two metal atoms forming a bridged structure (*h-111* and *h-100* modes in Figure 5b).

Figure 5. (a) Binding energy of molecular O_2 on neutral (empty symbols, dashed line) and anionic (full symbols, full line) Au_n clusters. Adapted with permission from [39]. Copyright 2003 Aemiraen Chemical Society. (b) Different modes of adsorption of molecular O_2 on metal clusters and nanoparticles. (c) Relationship between charge transferred to O_2 and $\nu(OO)$ stretching frequency calculated for silver (blue) and gold (red) clusters, nanoparticles and surfaces (c). The optimized geometries of the silver systems are also depicted. Adapted from ref. [40-42]

The interaction of molecular O_2 with gold, silver and copper catalysts involves a transfer of electron density from the metal to the empty antibonding $2\pi^*$ orbitals of O_2 , which produces a weakening of the O-O bond, a lengthening of the O-O distance, and a concomitant shift to lower values of the $\nu(OO)$ vibrational stretching frequency. The

direct correlation between the charge transferred and the shift in the $\nu(\text{OO})$ vibrational frequency is clearly observed in Figure 5c for gold (red squares) and silver (blue symbols), and evidences that very small clusters are not able to efficiently activate O_2 , probably due to their limited amount of electrons available to share. However, a deeper analysis of the optimized geometries of the adsorption complexes suggests that other factors are also playing a role in this process. The degree of charge transfer from the HOMO of the metal cluster to the LUMO of O_2 depends on the spatial overlap between the two orbitals, and this is related to the mode of adsorption of O_2 on the metal. Thus, the largest degree of charge transfer is found for O_2 adsorbed on the (100) facets of 3D clusters or nanoparticles, forming four M-O bonds, followed by adsorption onto (111) facets forming three M-O bonds. Adsorption of O_2 in a *bridge* mode leads to an intermediate degree of molecular activation, slightly larger on Ag_{38} than on the smallest clusters, while adsorption on *top* and *mono* conformations leads to a weak activation of the O-O bond.

These preliminary trends obtained with gold and silver were investigated in more detail for copper clusters of diverse size and morphology, in particular Cu_n clusters with $n = 3-8, 13$ and 38 atoms). [20, 43]. As described before, there are several Cu_n isomers per size close in energy for each value of n , including in some cases 2D and 3D structures for the same atomicity (Cu_5 and Cu_6 , see Figure 1), and their consideration allows separating the effect of cluster size from that of cluster morphology. The analysis of ~ 40 complexes formed by O_2 adsorption in different conformations on each of the eight Cu_n systems investigated confirmed that, as suggested by Au and Ag results, it is the adsorption mode and thus cluster morphology the main parameter determining the activation of the O_2 molecule upon adsorption. Figure 6a shows that, regardless of the number of atoms in the cluster, the largest shift in the $\nu(\text{OO})$ vibrational frequency, associated to a charge transfer $\geq 1e$, is found for the *h-100* or *h-111* adsorption modes, in agreement with the increased number of M-O bonds mentioned before. *Bridge* configurations always lead to a charge transfer of around $0.5e$ that results in $\nu(\text{OO})$ frequencies in the $950-1050 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ range, whereas *top* and *mono* modes provide the least activation in the trend (less than $0.5e$ transferred, $\nu(\text{OO})$ between 1100 and 1300 cm^{-1}).

Figure 6. DFT-calculated a) relationship between charge transferred to O₂ and $\nu(OO)$ stretching frequency (at the PW91 level with VASP) b) activation energies for O₂ dissociation with cluster size for Cu_n clusters ($3 < n < 8$ and 13, 38) at the B3PW91/Def2TZVP level with Gaussian09. TS structures are also shown. Adapted with permission from [20]. Copyright 2015 American Chemical Society. c) Gibbs free energy profile for dissociation of molecular O₂ into two adsorbed O atoms over 2D Cu₅ (purple,

solid lines) and 3D Cu₅ (purple, dashed lines). Reprinted with permission from [43]. Copyright 2017 American Chemical Society.

As it was previously pointed out, the shape of the frontier orbitals of planar copper clusters favors the interaction with reactants along their edges (recall Figure 1). Indeed, for 2D clusters we only found stable structures with O₂ adsorbed in *bridge*, *top* or *mono*-coordinated modes, among which *bridge* configurations provide the largest adsorption energies and also the largest degree of O₂ activation. In contrast, 3D clusters allow and favor the adsorption of the O₂ molecule in the more activating facet modes, i.e. *h-111* and *h-100*. Indeed, the charge transferred to the π^* orbital of O₂ in these facet modes produces superoxo species with elongated O-O bond distances ($\Delta r_{\text{oo}} \sim 0.28 \text{ \AA}$) while *bridge* modes stabilize peroxy species with smaller O-O bond elongations ($\Delta r_{\text{oo}} \sim 0.12 \text{ \AA}$).

In agreement with these molecular activation trends, the subsequent study of O₂ dissociation on all Cu_n clusters lead to systematically lower activation energies on 3D clusters irrespective of their size (see Figure 6b). As exemplified in Figure 6c for the 2D and 3D isomers of Cu₅, the activation energy barrier decreases from 41 kcal/mol on the planar cluster to only 15 kcal/mol on the 3D system, due to the combination of a more activated reaction minimum for the latter and a less-stabilized transition state geometry for the former. Indeed, the stabilization of TS by bridging the two oxygen atoms with two copper atoms is a general trend for 3D clusters (see Figure 6b). [20] Note also that O₂ dissociation over planar Cu₅ causes a morphological deformation of the cluster towards a 3D structure, highlighting the non-negligible effect of reactants and products on the geometrical and therefore electronic and catalytic properties of metal clusters. As explained before on the basis of the *s*-, *p*- and *d*- shells of the electronic structure of clusters, compact 3D structures are favored with increasing atomicity. As a result, activation energies for O₂ dissociation decrease with increasing size, but it is important to remark that the ultimate cause is the change in the cluster morphology, with the concomitant change in their electronic structure.

Another illustrative example on how the composition of the frontier molecular orbitals of metal clusters determines the geometry of molecular adsorption is based on some published [44] and other preliminary DFT results for the adsorption of iodobenzene on Pd₃, Pt₃ and Au₃ clusters. The interaction between iodobenzene and the metal clusters involves charge transfer from the HOMO of the molecule, characterized by a combination

of the p_z orbital of I with contributions from the aromatic ring, to the LUMO of the metal cluster, and back-donation from the metal HOMO to the aryl halide LUMO, which is an antibonding $\sigma^*(\text{C-I})$ centered along the C-I bond (Figure 7). The LUMO of Pd_3 is spread on the face of the cluster hence matching the HOMO of iodobenzene and thus directing the adsorption through the cycle (Figure 7). The LUMO of Pt_3 , in contrast, is symmetrically localized on two Pt atoms, at one of the edges of the cluster, while that of Au_3 mainly consists of one large lobe pointing outwards the cluster. As a result, iodobenzene adsorbs at the edge of the Pt_3 cluster forming bonds with the I atom and with four C atoms or the aromatic ring, while the interaction of iodobenzene with the Au_3 cluster only involves the I atom, that is mono-coordinated to the single Au atom contributing to the LUMO orbital. As regards back-donation, that introduces electron density into the antibonding $\sigma^*(\text{C-I})$ orbital thus weakening the C-I bond, it should in principle be efficient in all cases, given the similar composition and therefore possibility of overlapping of the HOMO of the three clusters considered.

Figure 7. Composition of the HOMO and LUMO orbitals of iodobenzene, Pd_3 , Pt_3 and Au_3 clusters, and most stable configuration of iodobenzene adsorbed on each cluster. Molecular orbital distributions of iodobenzene and the metal clusters were obtained with the Gaussian09 computer program [45] using the natural bond order (NBO) approach [46] at the B3LYP [47, 48]/LANL2DZ [49, 50] level.

In summary, the main features of the electronic distribution of isolated metal clusters are discrete energy levels, presence of a band gap making them non-metallic, and localized

molecular orbitals with large lobes fully accessible to interact with molecules. The close relationship between cluster size, shape, charge and electronic structure allows to infer that any change in one of these properties should modify, to a greater or lesser extent, some or the totality of the others. Since metal clusters need to be stabilized by protective ligands or deposited on an organic or inorganic support for their actual application in catalysis, the method used for their synthesis will necessarily have an impact on their properties.

3. Synthesis of Atomically Precise Metal Clusters

The synthesis of catalysts containing size-controlled metal clusters is challenging, not only because of the intrinsic difficulties to generate these metallic entities with a particular atomicity, but also due to the problems associated to the anchoring of the clusters on the solid support, the removal of the stabilizing ligands and the possible sintering of the clusters into larger particles. Very generally, clusters can be generated in gas-phase or in solution, to be later stabilized by a variety of systems.

To generate clusters in gas-phase the most common procedures employ a piece of the solid metal as the source to be eroded (via laser vaporization, magnetron sputtering or arc discharge), but liquid metal or liquid precursors can also be used with the electrospray ionization technique and metals of not very high boiling point (< 2000 K) can be directly vaporized via gas aggregation or supersonic expansion [11]. The cluster size selection among the wide size distribution that these techniques produce is achieved through mass spectrometers that separate the particles on the basis of their different charge and mass. As a matter of fact, this ability to discern cluster size has turned some of these spectrometries, such as electrospray ionization (ESI) and matrix-assisted laser desorption ionization (MALDI), into common techniques for cluster analysis [51-53]. Finally, the last step is cluster deposition, that is, to place the size-selected metal clusters on a surface. The velocity i.e. the kinetic energy that the gas-phase clusters approach the support with is very relevant, for with a high energy the cluster may suffer fragmentation, scatter or even implantate below the surface of the support (Figure 8a). [54] A slight increase in energy may however be beneficial to anchor the cluster to a surface in what is known as *pinning*, where the cluster displaces some atoms of the support. Nevertheless, to produce the so-called model catalysts, where the nature and size of the deposited clusters are as controlled as possible, low-energy cluster deposition is preferred. This is also known as

soft-landing (Figure 8b). [11] It is usually done in ultra-high vacuum conditions (UHV) and if gas phase clusters were ionized they become neutral losing their charge to the support upon deposition. Chemical vapor deposition (CVD) can be also applied, but soft-landing allows a higher control over the size of the clusters and their coverage of the support; CVD is usually employed to synthesize thin 2D films instead. [55-56]

Figure 8. Schemes of a) possible processes of high-energy cluster-surface impact, adapted with permission from [54]. Copyright 2003 IOP Publishing, b) soft-landing deposition of gas-phase clusters, adapted with permission from [11]. Copyright 2011

Elsevier, c) electrochemical synthesis, adapted with permission from [59]. Copyright 2005 American Chemical Society, d) two-phase Brust-Schiffin synthesis of gold clusters and e) synthesis of supported clusters with ligand-removal methods, adapted from with permission from [7]. Copyright 2016 Elsevier, and f) synthesis of dendrimer encapsulated clusters, adapted with permission from [74-78]. Copyright 2015 Springer Nature.

The generation of clusters in solution, also known as wet-chemistry approaches, include many different processes that generally involve the reduction of a salt or mononuclear precursor and produce clusters surrounded by stabilizers that prevent their agglomeration [4, 6-9, 12, 57].

The electrochemical synthesis was first employed by Reetz et al. in 1994 [58] to produce tetraalkylammonium-stabilized clusters of Pd of as low as 1.4 nm mean particle size. In this technique an anode of the desired metal is used as the source, producing metal cations that are reduced at the cathode and at the same time are stabilized by ligands from the solution (Figure 8c) [59]. The electrochemical method possess many advantages compared to the preparation of metal clusters by chemical reduction, as it requires low temperatures and cheaper materials, and the cluster size is more easily manipulated by tuning current, voltage, electrolyte and concentration of stabilizers [8, 60]. Using this technique Vilar-Vidal et al. were able to synthesize Cu_n clusters of $n \leq 14$ stabilized by TBAN, able to be dispersed in both polar and apolar solvents [31, 61] and very recently the synthesis of ligand-free Cu_5 clusters in water was achieved [62, 43].

The Brust-Schiffin method owes its name to the scientists of the Schiffin group that proposed the method again back in 1994. Originally a two-phase method [63], in this synthesis a phase-transfer reagent is used to transfer a chloro-metal salt from an aqueous phase to an organic phase, from which the clusters are produced through reduction with a reducing agent (usually NaBH_4) (Figure 8d). One-phase variants were later developed [8, 64]. Clusters synthesized this way are stabilized by the thiols employed in the organic phase. Since the S-Au interaction is strong, many studies can be found on Au clusters synthesized by this method, [6, 7, 8] but there are also examples for Ag, Cu, Pt and Pd clusters synthesized by the Brust-Schiffin method [8]. The surface properties of the resulting material can be controlled by adjusting experimental parameters such as the nature of the protecting ligands and the reducing agent, the metal to ligand ratio or the pH of the solution [6, 8]. In addition, the reaction temperature and time can also affect the

final size of the clusters, as illustrated in the production of Au₁₉ and Au₂₅ through a careful aging process by Jin and co-workers [65-67]. Similar chemical reduction processes can be used to produce gold clusters stabilized by phosphines instead of thiols [8], generally by reduction of triarylphosphine Au(I) complexes. The weaker interaction of phosphines facilitates the removal or exchange of ligands after preparation and their use as stabilizers is not exclusive of gold: small silver clusters (Ag₁₄, Ag₁₆) were synthesized by Yang et al. through a combination of phosphine and thiol ligands [68, 69].

It is worth noting that synthesis by chemical reduction can be carried out in a continuous flow as opposed to a batch, in what are called microfluidic, millifluidic or lab-on-a-chip procedures [70-73], also employed to produce other types of larger nanostructures for biomedical applications [74, 75]. The main idea of this synthesis procedure is to inject the precursor and the reducing agent at specific flow rates that allow their reaction from their converging point onwards. This way, the selected flow rate, capillar or channel length and/or reaction time can change the final size and morphology of the particles synthesized. Moreover, a spatial gradient of cluster growth can be produced, which allows its study in different time-resolution scales. Ligand-protected Au_n (n=1-11) clusters [2], gold nanoclusters of 1-2 nm [1] and copper clusters of ~ 1 nm [3] have been successfully synthesized employing these variants.

The ligand-protected clusters obtained as described above could in principle be directly employed in homogeneous catalysis, but the strong interaction with the ligand molecules and their high surface coverage usually impedes the adsorption of reactants. It is hence more common to deposit the clusters on a solid support and employ them as heterogeneous catalysts, since clusters are then stabilized by the surface of the support and ligands are no longer necessary (Figure 8e) [7]. While clusters can be deposited on a support after generation in solution, the synthesis in solution directly on the support by impregnation with precursors (salts or organometallic complexes) is one of the most common ways used to obtain supported metal clusters [13].

The decarbonylation of supported metal carbonyl clusters constitutes one of the first efforts that lead to Ir and Pt clusters along this line [12, 76, 77]. Thus, mononuclear metal carbonyl precursors (or preformed metal carbonyl clusters) on MgO or γ -Al₂O₃ metal oxides produce dispersed metal carbonyl clusters of the M_n(CO)_m form, from which supported clusters are obtained after the removal of CO ligands by heating in He or H₂. Stronger ligands such as thiolates and phosphines may require harder treatments for their

elimination, [7, 13] the most common of which is calcination. It eliminates organic ligands effectively, but entails the risk of cluster aggregation due to heat. Redox reactions and solvent extraction are softer and simpler treatments that can be used for ligands with determined solubilities or reactivities, respectively, while inorganic salt anions can be removed through washing and centrifugation. Besides, the nature of the selected support will also affect the final material upon these treatments; for instance, if the metal-support interaction (MSI) is not strong enough not only cluster aggregation but also cluster encapsulation by the support may be produced [13].

In spite of the options described, the complete ligand removal and the preservation of the clusters are known to be complicated both in their consecution and in their characterization, and impurities may remain which may decrease the catalytic activity of the final material [7, 13]. Metal oxides are the most common materials used as supports, both unreducible, when properties of the clusters are meant to be preserved as unmodified as possible (MgO, Al₂O₃) and reducible, when a certain MSI effect is pursued (CeO₂, TiO₂). However, mesoporous solids such as metal-organic-frameworks (MOFs) and zeolites (crystalline aluminosilicates) are also increasingly employed due to their advantageous confinement restrictions.

Indeed, the so-called template methods are another synthesis alternative where the metal clusters are formed within the interior of systems that act as a template or nano-reactor, which can precisely be MOFs or zeolites. Other systems include polymers, dendrimers and even microemulsions. The encapsulation favors the production of clusters with well-controlled size, while the various configurations and sites of the different templates can produce clusters with a certain desired morphology [8]. The procedure generally involves the incorporation or exchange of metal ions from solution to specific sites of the stabilizers, from which the clusters are produced in a subsequent reduction (Figure 8f). [78] As the H⁺ from solution can compete with the metal ions for the sites, the pH of the solution is an important variable. This otherwise simple synthesis method has the potential advantages of cluster size control, stability against cluster sintering and ligand-free surfaces of the clusters [8].

Microemulsions, which are produced in the mixture of two immiscible liquids, also behave like nanoreactors, but the method takes advantage of the exchange of material that occurs between different droplets of an emulsion to synthesize clusters by chemical reduction: one emulsion is prepared containing the metallic salt and another one with the

reducing agent [9]. While the droplet size can be controlled, obtaining small clusters is difficult and requires the optimization of several variables, such as the water-surfactant molar ratio or the concentrations of the salt and the reducing agent. Nevertheless, using this technique very small clusters of Ag ($n < 10$) and Cu ($n < 13$) were successfully synthesized [25, 9].

Finally, it is important to mention that the strong interaction between metal atoms and stabilizing ligands can cause the etching of particles. This can be purposely used to synthesize clusters from larger nanoparticles. [7, 8] These type of methodologies where clusters are produced from preformed larger systems are also classified as “top-down”, whereas those where clusters are obtained through aggregation and reduction are called “bottom-up”. The term “ship-in-the-bottle” is also used to differentiate template-based procedures from the other two approaches.

4. Identification of Metal Clusters as the Catalytically Active Species in Homogeneous Reactions

The fact that metal clusters can be formed in solution from the corresponding metal salts or metal organic complexes under certain reaction conditions raised concerns about the true nature, homogenous or heterogeneous, of the active species in reactions catalyzed by transition metal complexes in solution. [14, 79-85] One of the most challenging cases reported is the identification of the kinetically dominant active species in the classic hydrogenation of benzene and cyclohexene with molecular H₂, using [RhCp*Cl₂]₂ (Cp* = [η⁵-C₅(CH₃)₅]) complex as starting catalyst. Using a methodology that combines kinetic studies, especially searching for induction periods or sigmoidal kinetic curves, poisoning experiments, TEM measurements and other operando spectroscopic characterization techniques, it was established that at the milder reaction conditions employed for cyclohexene hydrogenation (22°C and 3.7 atm H₂) the catalyst was a monometallic homogeneous complex. In contrast, the harsher conditions required to hydrogenate the most stable benzene molecule (50-100°C, 50 atm H₂) led to the formation of traces of soluble Rh(0)_n nanoparticles and large amounts of sub nanometer Rh₄ clusters, the latter being the true heterogeneous catalyst. [86, 87]

The Ziegler-type hydrogenation catalysts, composed by a transition metal salt or complex pre-catalyst and an AlR₃ co-catalyst, are widely used in industry, mainly for polymer hydrogenation. With the objective of improving their catalytic performance, the compositional and structural nature of the catalytically active species in some Ziegler-type hydrogenation catalysts was investigated using detailed kinetic analysis, XRD, TEM, and other physico-chemical and spectroscopic characterization techniques. [83, 88, 89] Following this approach, Schmidt et al. [90] demonstrated that the Et₃Al-Co(acac)₂ catalytic system used in the hydrogenation of styrene and other olefins evolves under reaction conditions producing metallic Co nanoparticles with diameter between 2.5 and 5 nm. The surface of these nanoparticles is coated by anionic or neutral ligands such as Et₃Al, Et₂AlEt(acac), and the products of their transformations, which prevent their aggregation or sintering. The Al/Co ratio determines the composition of the stabilizing coating, and therefore the stability against agglomeration of the colloidal Co nanoparticles. But it also has an influence on the ability of the olefin reactant molecules to adsorb on the metallic centers and, in turn, on the global hydrogenation activity of the

catalytic system. With this information the Al/Co ratio was optimized to maximize the rate of styrene hydrogenation at different contents of crystallization water in the catalyst.

The formation of new C-C bonds through coupling reactions is a key process in organic synthesis, and has important practical applications in fine chemistry and pharmaceutical industries. [90-93] Cross-coupling reactions such as Heck, Suzuki, Sonogashira or Stille, which involve the activation of an aryl halide reactant and lead to formation of a new C-C bond, are typically and efficiently catalyzed by palladium salts and complexes in homogeneous phase, [94-96] but also by metallic nanoparticles as heterogeneous solid catalysts, [81, 82, 85, 97] and only recently the key role of small clusters composed by three or four palladium atoms it has been demonstrated. [98]

The accepted mechanism for Pd-catalyzed C-C bond forming reactions in homogeneous phase involves a Pd⁰/Pd^{II} redox cycle (Figure 9). The first step consists of an oxidative addition of the aryl halide reactant to a Pd⁰ centre, yielding a Pd^{II} intermediate complex that is subsequently attacked by a nucleophile species. In the Heck reaction (Figure 9a) the nucleophile is a terminal alkene that is inserted in the Pd-Ar bond. The olefinic product is generated by β -hydride elimination, and the presence of a base is required to regenerate the Pd⁰ active site. In other Pd-catalyzed cross-coupling reactions, a transmetalation step connects the main catalytic cycle in which the aryl halide adds to palladium and the new C-C bond is formed with a secondary cycle in which the partner reactant is activated. In the Suzuki reaction, the second reactant is an aryl boronic acid (Figure 9b) and the presence of a base is crucial for the reaction to proceed. In the Sonogashira coupling a terminal alkyne is activated on a co-catalyst, usually copper, in the presence of base, and is subsequently transferred to the palladium centre (Figure 9c). In the transmetalation step the organic group R becomes attached to the Pd^{II} centre substituting the halogen atom and, finally, the the new C-C bond is formed and the product desorbs in a reductive elimination step, regenerating the Pd⁰ active site. [92-94]

Cross-coupling reactions, and in particular the Heck reaction, are efficiently catalyzed by Pd complexes in homogeneous phase, by ligand-free palladium such as PdCl₂ or Pd(OAc)₂, by Pd NPs stabilized by polymers and dendrimers, and by Pd NPs supported on carbon, silica or metal oxides. It has been demonstrated that under reaction conditions all these catalysts tend to form soluble Pd⁰ colloids or small nanoparticles that are stabilized to some extent by the anions present in solution, and that act as reservoir of the

active Pd species. Pd^{2+} salts and complexes are reduced to Pd^0 by action of the reactant or solvent (Figure 9d), while in the case of heterogeneous catalysts it has been proposed that the aryl halide reactant attacks the Pd atoms at the NP surface producing leaching and generating monomeric Pd species in solution that then enter the homogenous catalytic cycle previously described. At the end of the cycle the Pd atoms can either enter a new catalytic cycle or be redeposited again on the Pd NP, following a “dissolution-redeposition equilibrium” mechanism (Figure 9e). If oxidative addition is slow the colloidal Pd species can grow into larger particles that precipitate as palladium black, leading to catalyst deactivation. [14, 80-82, 102] Therefore, the key point to optimize Pd based catalysts for cross-coupling reactions seemed to be to control the rates of release and recapture of the soluble active Pd species. However, it is still more crucial to identify the true nature of the soluble active Pd species responsible for the catalytic activity.

Figure 9. Mechanism for Pd-catalyzed cross-coupling reactions: a) Heck, b) Sonogashira, c) Suzuki. d) formation of metallic Pd^0 from Pd^{II} salts or complexes in solution. e) dissolution-redeposition mechanism for Pd nanoparticles.

To this purpose, Corma et al. studied in detail the kinetics of the Heck, Sonogashira, Suzuki and Stille cross-coupling reactions using different homogeneous and heterogeneous Pd-based pre-catalysts, and characterized the evolution of the Pd species by TEM, dynamic light scattering (DLS), electrospray ionization mass spectrometry (ESIMS), matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF) and UV-Vis spectroscopy. [98] Under typical Heck reaction conditions, 135°C and N-methylpyrrolidone as solvent, a sigmoidal kinetic curve was obtained for the coupling of Br-cyclo-octene with butyl acrylate using either Pd(OAc)₂ or Pd NPs of 3.9 nm diameter as catalysts (Figure 10a). TEM and DLS measurements showed that Pd(OAc)₂ decomposes in a few minutes to form Pd NPs with diameter between 2 and 10 nm. However, the induction period continues for two hours, a delay similar to that observed when Pd NPs are used as the starting catalyst. To establish the nature of the true catalytic active species, the reaction in the presence of Pd NPs was monitored by simultaneous GC-MS analysis and absorption/emission UV-Vis spectroscopy. During the induction period, only the nonfluorescence plasmon band at ~420 nm corresponding to Pd nanoparticles was observed, but as soon as the reaction started a new band at 350-350 nm appeared in the adsorption spectra together with a clear fluorescence band at 450 nm upon irradiation, with its intensity increasing in parallel with the reaction rate (Figure 10b). Mass spectrometry analysis of the samples before and after the induction period indicated that the reaction started only when small Pd₃ and Pd₄ clusters appeared in the reaction medium, these clusters being responsible for the fluorescence emission and for the catalytic activity. Interestingly, when the reaction was carried out in the presence of 1% water, the induction period disappeared (Figure 10a, blue triangles) and the same adsorption and emission bands at 450 nm were observed from the beginning of the reaction. Further inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectroscopy (ICP-AES) analysis of the reaction mixture at different times showed that, in the absence of water, the amount of palladium leached to the solution is very low and occurs through oxidative addition of the bromoarene to the Pd atoms at the surface of the nanoparticle, as previously proposed [14, 80-82, 102] and depicted in Figure 9e. In the presence of water, however, the dislodging of Pd atoms from the nanoparticle surface is much more efficient and produces stable solvated Pd₃ and Pd₄ clusters. This knowledge allowed the ex situ preparation of sub nanometer Pd clusters by adding Pd NPs to an aqueous solution of NMP, the storage of such clusters in aqueous solution for long periods, and their subsequent use in cross-coupling reactions without loss of catalytic properties.

Figure 10. (a) Conversion of Br-cyclo-octene by reaction with butyl acrylate using either anhydrous Pd(OAc)₂ (green rhombus) anhydrous Pd NPs (red squares) or Pd NPs with 1% water (blue triangles) as catalyst and (b) UV/Vis fluorescence emission spectra (irradiation wavelength: 370 nm) measured for the anhydrous Pd(OAc)₂ and Pd NPs at different time intervals. The emission spectrum obtained for the aqueous Pd NPs sample is similar to that at the maximum rate. Reprinted with permission from [98]. Copyright 2013 John Wiley and Sons.

A similar procedure combining detailed kinetic studies with adsorption/emission UV-Vis spectroscopy and MALDI-TOF characterization was used by Corma et al. to identify small Au₃-Au₁₀ clusters formed from several Au^I and Au^{III} salts and complexes in solution as the true catalytically active species in different organic reactions. Thus, small Au₃-Au₅ clusters are formed in the presence of alkynes, and catalyze the ester-assisted hydration of alkynes with TOF as high as 10⁵, while Au₈-Au₉ clusters are specifically active for the bromination of arenes. [96] An important limitation of these systems for industrial application is that the extremely active clusters are formed *in situ* under certain reaction conditions, and despite their excellent performance under these conditions, they usually evolve to larger and non-active species that cannot be recovered nor reused in subsequent cycles. Heterogenization of metal clusters by supporting them on solid carriers is therefore of major interest.

5. Metal-Support Interaction in Heterogeneous Catalysts

To prepare active heterogeneous catalysts, clusters can be supported on solid organic and inorganic materials such as metal oxides, zeolites, carbon based materials and metal

organic frameworks (MOFs), and in all cases the metal-support interaction responsible for stabilizing the metal clusters provokes changes in their geometry, electronic structure and catalytic properties.

5.1. Organic supports

Metal-organic frameworks (MOFs), with a porous 3D structure formed by inorganic nodes and organic linkers, have recently emerged as very versatile materials to encapsulate small metal clusters with precise geometrical and electronic properties. [104-106] As a case study of MOF-supported metal clusters, we describe an heterogeneous catalyst consisting of Pd₄ clusters with mixed-valence 0/+1 oxidation states homogeneously distributed and stabilized within the walls of an anionic metal-organic framework, and its application to several carbene-mediated reactions of diazoacetates. [105] The three-step synthesis of the catalyst (see Figure 11a) starts with a preformed, highly porous anionic MOF of formula Mg^{II}₂{Mg^{II}₄[Cu^{II}₂(Me₃mpba)₂]₃} · 45H₂O (**1**) where Me₃mpba⁴⁻ = *N,N'*-2,4,6-trimethyl-1,3-phenylenebis(oxamate). This anionic MOF is converted by transmetallation into the more robust Ni^{II}₂{Ni^{II}₄[Cu^{II}₂(Me₃mpba)₂]₃} · 54H₂O (**2**). The exchange of the Ni²⁺ cations hosted in the pores by [Pd^{II}(NH₃)₄]²⁺ cations yields the novel compound [Pd^{II}(NH₃)₄][Pd^{II}₂(μ-O)(NH₃)₆(NH₄)₂]_{0.5}{Ni^{II}₄[Cu^{II}₂(Me₃mpba)₂]₃} · 52H₂O (**3**) that is finally reduced with NaBH₄ to give Pd₂@Na₃{Ni^{II}₄[Cu^{II}₂(Me₃mpba)₂]₃} · 56H₂O (**4**) catalyst, which contains the [Pd₄]²⁺ clusters (see Figure 11a). Resolution of the crystal structure of catalyst **4** d using single-crystal X-ray diffraction techniques allowed the observation of quasi-linear [Pd₄]²⁺ clusters stabilized in the hydrophilic octagonal pores present in the walls of the large MOF channels (see Figure 11b). The inner Pd-Pd bond lengths in the linear cluster are significantly shorter (2.44-2.57 Å) than the outer ones (2.91-3.16 Å), and deconvolution of the XPS spectra shows the typical peak for Pd⁰ at a binding energy of BE(Pd3d_{5/2}) = 335.7 eV together with a non-ordinary peak at BE(Pd3d_{5/2}) = 337.0 eV that was attributed to Pd⁺. In order to confirm the unusual structure and electronic nature of the [Pd₄]²⁺ clusters arising from the XRD and XPS data, the geometry and charge distribution of a simplified Pd₄{Ni₄[Cu₂(Me₃mpba)₂]₃}²⁻ model was investigated using DFT calculations (Figure 11c). It was found that when the positions of Pd atoms are optimized without restrictions within the octagonal pore of the MOF, they approach the donor oxygen atoms of the wall forming strong bonds with typical Pd-O distances of

2.30-2.37 Å, and optimized Pd–Pd distances of 2.69 and 2.65 Å for the outer and inner bonds, respectively. Despite this result apparently contradicts the quasi-linear geometry of the $[\text{Pd}_4]^{2+}$ clusters determined by XRD, overlapping and averaging of the two equivalent structures obtained from the DFT optimization yields a slightly bent, yet linear Pd_4 unit with longer outer Pd-Pd distances (2.40 versus 2.16 Å for outer and inner Pd-Pd bond lengths). Bader analysis of the charge distribution reveals a mixed-valence state $\text{Pd}^+\text{Pd}^0\text{Pd}^0\text{Pd}^+$, with the positive charge preferentially located on the terminal Pd atoms and separated by the two central metallic atoms. Taking advantage of the stability of these homogeneously distributed Pd^+ species in the $[\text{Pd}_4]^{2+}$ -MOF **4**, its catalytic performance was tested in some representative carbene-mediated processes such as the inter- and intramolecular Buchner reaction between benzene derivatives and diazoacetates. The Buchner reaction is only catalyzed by dirhodium salts and some particular copper complexes, but the unusual electronic structure of Pd in the $[\text{Pd}_4]^{2+}$ -MOF catalyst **4** efficiently promotes this reaction with good activity and selectivity. Interestingly, when the pre-catalyst **3** containing only Pd^{2+} species was tested in the reaction of benzene with ethyl diazoacetate, an induction period of ~30 min was observed, after which the reaction started and proceeded at a similar rate as that obtained with **4**. This behavior indicates that ethyl diazoacetate acts as a reducing agent that converts **3** into **4** under reaction conditions as NaBH_4 does externally, and highlights the fact that one of the major issues associated to catalysis by metal clusters, which is the possible formation of the true catalytic species under reaction conditions, is common for homogeneous and heterogeneous catalysis.

Figure 11. (a) Synthesis of $\text{Pd}_2@ \text{Na}_3\{\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}_4[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}_2(\text{Me}_3\text{mpba})_2\}_3\} \cdot 56\text{H}_2\text{O}$ catalyst showing the structures of compounds **1-4** determined by single-crystal X-ray diffraction. (b) Perspective views of the channels of compound **4** along the *c* (top) and *a* (bottom) axis. Cu, Mg, and Ni atoms are depicted as blue, orange and yellow polyhedra, Pt atoms are depicted as purple spheres. (c) DFT optimized geometries of a Pd_4 cluster in a $\text{Pd}_4\{\text{Ni}_4[\text{Cu}_2(\text{Me}_3\text{mpba})_2\}_3\}^{2-}$ model. The two equivalent optimized structures (top) and the overlapped and averaged systems (bottom) are shown. Pd, Cu, Ni, N, O, C and H atoms are depicted as blue, green, pink, purple, red, orange and white balls, respectively. Adapted with permission from [105]. Copyright 2017 Springer Nature.

This is indeed the case for the oxidation of thiophenol to disulfide with molecular O₂ using as starting catalyst a solid material consisting of isolated gold atoms supported on functionalized carbon nanotubes. [107] The catalyst synthesis is based on the reaction of HAuCl₄ with the amino groups of the polyallylamine hydrochloride (PAH) polyelectrolyte used to functionalize the carbon nanotubes, and the subsequent addition of sodium citrate, which acts as reducing agent and stabilizer. The first reduction step that converts Au³⁺ into Au⁺ and oxidizes the citrate anion to dicarboxyacetone is fast, but the second step in which Au⁺ is reduced to Au⁰ is much slower, and it is possible to avoid the growth of metallic nanoparticles by controlling the gold content and the citrate/Au ratio. [108] Following this procedure, isolated Au⁺ species stabilized by dicarboxyacetone and amino or hydroxyl ligands were synthesized (sample A in Figure 12) and their catalytic activity in the oxidation of thiophenol to disulfide was tested. The reaction with sample A presented an initial induction period of about 6 min, after which disulfide was formed at a high reaction rate, with about 85% conversion being reached after 1 hour (Figure 12a, top). The observation of an induction period indicates that the active species are not the isolated gold atoms initially present in the as prepared catalyst, but others generated during the reaction. To unravel their nature, the evolution of the gold species under reaction conditions was followed by stopping the reaction at different times (B, C, D in Figure 12a, top), taking catalyst samples, characterizing them by HAADF-STEM and UV/vis spectroscopy, and reusing them with fresh feed of thiophenol and O₂. No induction period was observed when samples B (taken at 6min) and C (taken at 12 min) were used with fresh feed (see Figure 12a, bottom), but the activity of the latter was low, and sample D taken after 1 hour reaction was completely inactive. The microscopy images (Figure 12b) show that while the fresh catalyst is mostly composed by isolated gold atoms, in the most active sample B gold clusters containing from 4 to 13 atoms are the main species observed. As reaction proceeds, metal aggregation occurs and both gold clusters and nanoparticles are observed on sample C, while in sample D about 90% of gold has aggregated into nanoparticles larger than 2 nm, that are not active.

To understand why neither isolated gold atoms nor larger particles, but only small gold clusters are active in the oxidation of thiophenol, the reaction mechanism was theoretically investigated at the B3LYP/LANL2DZ level. It was found that the dicarboxyacetone stabilized Au⁺ atoms initially present in the catalyst are partially reduced by reaction with two thiophenol molecules to form a negatively charged di-

thiolate gold complex from which it is not possible to create the new S-S bond (see Figure 13a). Neither such complex nor any of the previous reactant or intermediates is able to interact and activate O₂ because, as previously discussed, the poor overlap between the LUMO of O₂ and the HOMO of the gold species (depicted in Figure 13b) does not allow the required charge transfer to O₂. In contrast, O₂ is efficiently activated by small gold clusters such as Au₃ and Au₅ (see Figure 13c), and co-adsorption of the two reactants enhances the charge transfer from thiolate to oxygen, making possible the formation of the S-S bond. The final agglomeration of the gold clusters into nanoparticles and their passivation by too strongly bonded thiولات explain the decay in catalytic activity with time.

Figure 12. Yield of disulfide with time for catalyst samples taken at different reaction times (a) and HAADF-STEM images of these catalyst samples (b). Adapted with permission from [107]. Copyright 2013 Springer Nature.

Figure 13. DFT study of the reaction mechanism. (a) Optimized structures of selected intermediates involved in the oxidation of thiophenol catalyzed by Au^+ species and (b) atomic distribution of the HOMO of these structures. (c). Structures participating in the mechanism catalyzed by a Au_3 cluster. Gold, sulfur, carbon, oxygen and hydrogen atoms are depicted as yellow, blue, orange, red and white spheres, respectively. Adapted with permission from [107]. Copyright 2013 Springer Nature.

5.2. Metal Oxides

As the interaction of metal clusters with metal oxides is less specific than with the organic ligands composing the framework of MOFs or the supporting polymers, an heterogeneity in the size, morphology and electronic nature of metal species usually exists in solid catalysts that employ metal oxides as support. Seeking to minimize this complexity, model catalysts consist of size-controlled metal clusters deposited, at well-defined surface coverages, on clean, vacuum-annealed or thin films of metal oxides or on carbon-based materials. They are used to identify the parameters governing catalytic activity, to confirm proposals from theory, to accurately characterize the properties of the true active sites, or to analyze separately the effect of every variable relevant for the catalytic process, such as metal cluster size, morphology, charge state of the metal or the support, and presence of defects or adsorbed species. The actual understanding of catalysis by clusters is largely based on studies performed on model catalysts.

A most relevant and widely studied case is the activation of molecular O₂ with metal particles and clusters. In a sustainable chemistry context, the possibility to carry out oxidation reactions using molecular O₂ as the oxidant species, and generating water as the only byproduct, is one of the great challenges of catalysis. The discovery by Haruta et al.[109] that small gold nanoparticles finely dispersed on TiO₂ or α -Fe₂O₃ promote the low temperature oxidation of CO, and that the catalytic activity increases sharply for particles with diameter below 4 nm, led to a plethora of studies aiming to understand the main factors determining the catalytic performance of gold. Investigations on size-selected Au_n clusters with $n \leq 20$ soft-landed on thin films of MgO epitaxially grown on a Mo(100) surface and annealed at different temperatures to generate different densities of oxygen vacancies (F centers) evidenced the key role of cluster charging on the catalytic activity of gold for CO oxidation. [110, 111] With the assistance of quantum chemistry first-principles simulations it was shown that charge transfer from the electron-rich F centers in defective MgO to the supported gold clusters is necessary to bind and activate O₂, with clusters deposited on close-to-perfect MgO surfaces remaining chemically inert. In addition, these defect sites anchor strongly the supported gold clusters, inhibiting their sintering into larger and inactive particles.

The influence of the gold particle morphology on the catalytic activity for CO oxidation was investigated in detail by Goodman et al. [112-114] using different Au/TiO₂ model catalysts and a combination of kinetic studies with high-resolution Scanning Tunneling Microscopy (STM) and Spectroscopy (STS) data. Gold clusters with a relatively narrow size distribution and specific morphology, that is, with one, two or three atomic layers in thickness, as well as models consisting of well-ordered gold monolayers and bilayers that completely wet the oxide support, were deposited on stoichiometric and highly reduced TiO₂(110) surfaces (see Figure 14). Gold clusters were found to initially nucleate at surface oxygen vacancy defects, and to bind stronger to the reduced TiO₂(110) surfaces grown on a Mo(112) substrate, in agreement with Landman et al. [110, 111]. On the other hand, it was found that the intrinsic rate of CO oxidation, measured by the Turnover Frequency (TOF), not only depends on particle size, but especially on particle morphology, with the gold bilayer structure being significantly more active (by more than one order of magnitude) than the monolayer, or than other 2D clusters (see Figure 14).

High-resolution STM in combination with DFT calculations was also applied to analyze the influence of the oxidation and hydration state of the TiO₂(110) support on the

nucleation of gold clusters at different temperatures [115]. A reduced $\text{TiO}_2(110)$ sample containing electron-rich oxygen vacancy defects, a hydrated surface covered by bridged hydroxyl groups, and an oxidized model catalyst with oxygen adatoms located on the Ti troughs were exposed to a 3% ML of gold. At room temperature gold clusters nucleated homogeneously on the terraces of the reduced and oxidized supports, and at the step edges of the hydrated surface. But after subsequent heating of the reduced and oxidized samples, gold sintering to form larger particles was only observed in the reduced $\text{Au/TiO}_2(110)$ model catalyst, not in the oxidized one. According to DFT calculations performed to explain the experimental observations, only Au_1 and Au_3 clusters bind relatively strongly to oxygen vacancy defects forming Au-Ti bonds, the others explored (Au_2 , Au_4 , Au_5 and Au_7) binding very weakly. In contrast, and due to a partial charge transfer from the gold clusters to the surface oxygen atoms, Au-O bonds are formed in the oxidized $\text{Au/TiO}_2(110)$ catalyst. The gold clusters become cationic and therefore ionic bonding contributes to the enhanced stability on the oxidized support.

However, the complexity of the real heterogeneous catalysts makes the identification of the true active species among the many present in the material particularly challenging. Herzing et al. used aberration-corrected transmission electron microscopy to analyze the gold species present in a series of Au/FeO_x samples exhibiting very different activity in the CO oxidation reaction. [116] The improvement in the resolution of the HAADF images from the use of an aberration corrected STEM probe allowed to identify, besides gold nanoparticles in the 2-15 nm range, isolated gold atoms, small clusters with 0.2-0.3 nm diameter and one layer thick, and bilayer gold clusters with a diameter of ~ 0.5 nm. The correlation between catalytic activity and relative population of each of these species allowed to identify bilayer gold clusters of ~ 0.5 nm diameter and containing ~ 10 atoms as the true catalytic species in the oxidation of CO.

Just two years later, a highly active Au/FeO_x catalyst was synthesized by colloidal deposition of gold nanoparticles with diameter in the 2-5 nm range. [117] High-angle annular dark-field scanning transmission electron microscopy (HAADFSTEM) was used to accurately determine the particle size after deposition, (2.1 ± 0.54) nm, the thickness of the supported clusters (up to four layers), and to confirm the absence of gold clusters with diameter below 1 nm. After a thermal activation in the first reaction cycle to burn away the protecting agent used in the synthesis of the gold colloid, the catalyst showed a very high activity for the low temperature (-14°C) CO oxidation that did not decrease in

successive runs. These results, as well as those recently presented by He et al. [118] suggest that each of the different species present in a heterogeneous catalyst can have a non-equivalent catalytic activity, and that a size-dependent activity hierarchy must exist, at least in Au/FeOx catalyst for CO oxidation.

Figure 14. Catalytic activity for CO oxidation measured by the TOF, STM images of Au/TiO₂(110) catalysts, and schematic representations of (a) one, two and three atomic-layers thick gold particles on TiO₂(110) and (b) monolayer and bilayer gold structures on TiO₂(110)/Mo(112). Adapted with permission from [114]. Copyright 2006 American Chemical Society.

Cluster size and morphology are not the only factors influencing catalytic activity and, as discussed before, they are closely correlated with the electronic structure of the metal

clusters. This was clearly demonstrated by Kaden et al. [119] for the oxidation of CO catalyzed by Pd_n clusters (with n = 1, 2, 4, 7, 10, 16, 20 and 25) that were size-selected in the gas phase and deposited on a clean, vacuum-annealed rutile TiO₂(111) surface. The electronic structure of Pd in each sample was characterized by X-ray photoemission spectroscopy (XPS), and a non-monotonically trend was observed in the shift of the 3d BE relative to bulk Pd as a function of cluster size. Exactly the same trend was observed in the catalytic activity for CO oxidation: it was null for single Pd atoms, increased substantially for Pd₂ and declined smoothly as cluster size increased to Pd₇. For larger clusters activity increased monotonically independently of the appearance of bilayer structures, and dropped again for Pd₂₅. These results demonstrated that it is the electronic structure of Pd, characterized by the core-level binding energy shifts, the main factor controlling the CO oxidation activity of Pd/TiO₂ catalysts.

In catalysis, selectivity is at least as important as activity, and the tunable properties of supported metal clusters can be adjusted to improve the yield of some particularly elusive products. Propene oxide is a valuable precursor in the chemical industry of polymers, and many efforts are being done to develop an efficient and environmentally benign process for the direct epoxidation of propene with O₂. [120, 121] DFT studies of the reaction mechanism on silver catalyst models showed that the first and rate determining step of the reaction is the dissociation of molecular O₂. [42, 122] In subsequent steps, propene reacts with adsorbed O atoms either forming an oxametallacycle (OMC) intermediate precursor of the desired PO, or via H transfer generating a reactive allyl intermediate that is converted into acrolein and finally CO₂. (see Figure 15a) Attempts to improve the selectivity to PO by controlling the silver crystallographic facet exposed [122] or by decreasing silver particle size [42] failed, and led to the conclusion that pure silver catalysts are not intrinsically selective towards propene epoxidation with O₂ or H₂/O₂ mixtures irrespective of their particle size. In contrast, sub nanometer Ag₃ clusters deposited by soft-landing on an amorphous alumina support, as well as stable Ag aggregates of ~3.5 nm diameter formed under reaction conditions, are active for propene epoxidation yielding a negligible amount of CO₂ at low temperatures [see Figure 15b]. The key role of the active sites at the interface between the silver clusters and the alumina support was established both theoretically and experimentally. [123, 124] The DFT calculated activation energies for O₂ dissociation and epoxidation are lower at these interfacial sites (Figure 15c) and, although the unselective route producing acrolein and

CO₂ is also energetically favored, it requires a high oxygen coverage and therefore PO formation becomes competitive. On the other hand, silver clusters deposited by soft-landing on an Ultrananocrystalline Diamond (UNCD) support and treated exactly as the active alumina-supported silver catalysts were found inactive in the oxidation of propene. In situ Grazing Incidence X-ray Scattering (GISAXS) allowed to observe the aggregation of the UNCD-supported Ag₃ clusters into Ag nanoparticles of ~3.5 nm diameter, which didn't show any measurable activity either, thus confirming the key role of the metal-oxide interfacial sites.

Figure 15. (a) Schematic representation of the mechanism of propene epoxidation on silver catalysts. (b) Selectivity to propene oxide, acrolein and CO₂ versus temperature on alumina-supported Ag₃ clusters (top) and ~3.5 nm Ag aggregates (bottom). Adapted with permission from [123]. Copyright 2010 American Association for the Advancement of Science. Energy profile for O₂ dissociation at alumina-supported Au₁₉ top (black) and

interfacial (red) sites, and optimized structures of the clean model, adsorbed O₂ and product of dissociation. Adapted with permission from [124]. Copyright 2014 American Chemical Society.

Copper-based catalysts have also been investigated as potentially selective oxidation catalysts, and it has been found that the formation of copper oxide domains under reaction conditions strongly affects their catalytic performance. In the particular case of alkene epoxidation, where a certain surface coverage of oxygen is needed for the reaction to proceed, it has been reported that metallic copper exhibits a high selectivity to the epoxide that drops when the catalyst surface becomes oxidized. [124, 125] Taking advantage of the light-induced reduction of Cu by photoexcitation of its localized surface plasmon resonance, Linic et al. succeeded in the stabilization of metal copper species under propene epoxidation reaction conditions, which resulted in an increase in the selectivity to PO from 20% to 50%. [126] Following a different approach, we recently demonstrated the possibility to stabilize metallic copper species under oxidation reaction conditions by adjusting the atomicity of sub nanometer copper clusters. [43] Based on the clear reactivity trend previously obtained from DFT calculations (Figure 6) according to which O₂ dissociation is sensitive to cluster morphology, and on new computed data for the recombination of atomic oxygen and its desorption from oxidized clusters, it was proposed that planar Cu₅ clusters should be more resistant against oxidation and easier to reduce than 3D clusters of similar size. To confirm the theoretical proposal, three samples composed of average Cu₅, Cu₈ and Cu₂₀ clusters were synthesized electrochemically in the absence of stabilizing ligands and supported on a N-doped graphene film grown on a quartz plate. The trends in their ability to become oxidized in the presence of O₂ and to release oxygen and be reduced again under N₂ atmosphere closing the redox cycle were investigated by combining XPS and surface enhanced Raman spectroscopy (SERS), and the results fully confirmed the theoretical proposal. The possible effect of water on the reactivity of copper clusters was also investigated and it was found that, while the most inert Cu₅ clusters are not able to activate neither O₂ nor H₂O separately at 25°C, they efficiently catalyze the dissociation of the O-O bond in a mixture of only 3% H₂O in O₂ flow. The reaction pathway obtained from DFT calculations for co-adsorbed O₂ and H₂O (see Figure 16) involves a low-energy demanding H transfer from H₂O to O₂ generating stable adsorbed -OH and -OOH groups that, through several rearrangement steps and after addition of a second water molecule, provoke the rupture of the O-O bond.

In apparent contradiction with these results, Scanning Tunneling Microscopy revealed that the compact and lowest energy Cu(111) surface decomposes into clusters after exposure to CO, in a process that activates the surface for water dissociation on the low coordinated Cu atoms. [127] This discrepancy about the copper ability to dissociate water is explained by the different nature of the clusters in the two studies, i. e., defects associated with low-coordinated atoms on a metallic Cu surface in the Eren et al. work, [127] and isolated non-metallic Cu₅ clusters dispersed on an inert support in our study [43], and stresses the key role of the electronic structure of metal clusters of low atomicity in determining their catalytic properties. The sensitivity of subnanometer metal clusters to the surrounding environment, that is, to the nature of the material where they are supported, has been recently evidenced by a joint theoretical and experimental investigation of the redox properties of small Cu₄, Cu₁₂ and Cu₂₀ clusters. By combining first-principles calculations and XANES measurements Mammen et al. [128] confirmed that, in the gas phase, smaller Cu clusters are more resistant to oxidation. However, upon deposition on an alumina support, the trend is reversed and the smallest Cu₄ clusters are the most easily oxidized. All these findings open the possibility of an accurate control of the oxidation state and therefore of the catalytic properties of copper clusters not only by tuning their atomicity but also by optimizing the nature of the material used to support them.

Figure 16. DFT Gibbs free energy profiles for O₂ dissociation over Cu₅ clusters in the absence (solid lines) and presence (dashed lines) of water (a) and optimized structures

involved in the water-assisted dissociation of O₂ over a Cu₅ cluster (b). Reprinted with permission from [43]. Copyright 2017 American Chemical Society.

6. Conclusion

Metal clusters exhibit unique catalytic properties determined by a number of closely correlated variables, such as cluster atomicity, morphology, oxidation state and electronic structure. They can be formed *in situ* under reaction conditions from mononuclear precursors and larger nanoparticles, or synthesized with atomic precision using surface science techniques. In all cases, a major issue for their application in catalysis is to avoid their sintering and consequent deactivation, for which they are usually supported on organic or inorganic solids including polymers, metal-organic frameworks, zeolites and metal oxides. The sensitivity of sub nanometer metal clusters to the surrounding environment opens the possibility to modulate their electronic and catalytic properties through an accurate control of the metal-support interaction. This is the key point in the design and successful application of specific catalysts for particularly demanding reactions. Selected examples have been used to illustrate some of the most relevant challenges and efforts towards this goal, and to highlight the potential of this still emerging research field.

Acknowledgement

This work was supported by the Spanish Government through “Severo Ochoa Program” (SEV 2012-0267; SEV-2016-0683) and MAT2017-82288-C2-1-P. Red Española de Supercomputación (RES) and Centre de Càlcul de la Universitat de Valencia are gratefully acknowledged for computational resources and technical support. E.F. thanks the Spanish MINECO for her fellowship SVP-2013-068146.

References

- [1] Halder A, Curtiss L A, Fortunelli A and Vajda S 2018 Perspective: Size selected clusters for catalysis and electrochemistry *J. Chem. Phys.* **148** 110901 – 110901-15
- [2] Tyo E C and Vajda S 2015 Catalysis by clusters with precise numbers of atoms *Nat. Nanotechnol.* **10** 577–588
- [3] Liu L and Corma A 2018 Metal Catalysts for Heterogeneous Catalysis: From Single Atoms to Nanoclusters and Nanoparticles *Chem. Rev.* **118** 4981-5079
- [4] Liu X and Astruc D 2018 Atomically precise copper nanoclusters and their applications *Coor. Chem. Rev.* **359** 112-126

- [5] Lin C A J, Lee C H, Hsieh J T, Wang H H, Li J K, Shen J L, Chan W H, Yeh H I and Chang W H 2009 Synthesis of fluorescent metallic nanoclusters toward biomedical application: Recent progress and present challenges *J. Med. Biol. Eng.* **29** 276–283
- [6] Kurashige W, Niihori Y, Sharma S and Negishi Y 2016 Precise synthesis, functionalization and application of thiolate-protected gold clusters *Coor. Chem. Rev.* **320-321** 238–250
- [7] Fang J, Zhang B, Yao Q, Yang Y, Xie J and Yan N 2016 Recent advances in the synthesis and catalytic applications of ligand protected, atomically precise metal nanoclusters *Coor. Chem. Rev.* **322** 1–29
- [8] Lu Y and Chen W 2012 Sub-nanometre sized metal clusters: from synthetic challenges to the unique property discoveries *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **41** 3594–3623
- [9] Buceta D, Piñeiro Y, Vázquez-Vázquez C, Rivas J and López-Quintela M 2014 Metallic Clusters: Theoretical Background, Properties and Synthesis in Microemulsions. *Catalysts* **4** 356–374
- [10] Alonso J A 2000 Electronic and Atomic Structure, and Magnetism of Transition-Metal Clusters. *Chem. Rev.* **100** 637-677
- [11] Popok V N, Barke I, Campbell E. E. B. and Meiwes-Broer K-H 2011 Cluster-surface interaction: From soft landing to implantation *Surf. Sci. Rep.* **66** 347-377
- [12] Serna P and Gates B C 2014 Molecular Metal Catalysts on Supports: Organometallic Chemistry Meets Surface Science *Acc. Chem. Res.* **47** 2612–2620
- [13] Guo Y and Zhang Y W 2018 Metal Clusters Dispersed on Oxide Supports: Preparation Methods and Metal-Support Interactions *Topics in Catalysis* **61** 855–874
- [14] Crabtree R H 2012 Resolving Heterogeneity Problems and Impurity Artifacts in Operationally Homogeneous Transition Metal Catalysts *Chem. Rev.* **112** 1536–1554
- [15] Pyykkö P 1988 Relativistic effects in structural chemistry *Chem. Rev.* **88** 563
- [16] Häkkinen H 2008 Atomic and electronic structure of gold clusters: understanding flakes, cages and superatoms from simple concepts *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **37** 1847–1859
- [17] Song W, Lu W C, Wang C Z and Ho K M 2011 Magnetic and electronic properties of the nickel clusters Nin ($n \leq 30$) *Comp. Theor. Chem.* **978** 41–46
- [18] Kalita B and Deka R C 2007 Stability of small Pd_n, $n=1-7$ clusters on the basis of structural and electronic properties: A density functional approach *J. Chem. Phys.* **127** 244306
- [19] Chaves A S, Rondina G G, Piotrowski M J, Tereshchuk P and Da Silva J L F 2014 The Role of Charge States in the Atomic Structure of Cun and Ptn ($n = 2-14$ atoms) Clusters: A DFT Investigation *J. Phys. Chem. C* **118** 10813-10821
- [20] Fernandez E, Boronat M and Corma A 2015 Trends in the Reactivity of Molecular O₂ with Copper Clusters: Influence of Size and Shape *J. Phys. Chem. C* **119** 19832-19846.
- [21] Itoh M, Kumar V, Adschiri T and Kawazoe Y 2009 Comprehensive study of sodium, copper, and silver clusters over a wide range of sizes $2 \leq N \leq 75$ *J. Chem. Phys.* **131** 174510
- [22] Häkkinen H and Landman U 2000 Gold clusters .AuN, $2 \leq N \leq 10$. and their anions *Phys. Rev. B* **62** R2287
- [23] Häkkinen, H, Yoon B, Landman U, Li X, Zhai H-J and Wang L-S 2003 On the Electronic and Atomic Structures of Small AuN⁻ ($N = 4-14$) Clusters: A

- Photoelectron Spectroscopy and Density-Functional Study *J. Phys. Chem. A* **107** 6168–6175
- [24] Lecoultre S, Rydlo A, Felix C, Buttet J, Gilb S and Harbich W 2011 Optical Absorption of Small Copper Clusters in Neon: Cu_n (n=1-9) *J. Chem. Phys.* **134** 074303 - 074303-9
- [25] Vazquez-Vazquez C, Banobre-Lopez M, Mitra A, Lopez-Quintela M A and Rivas J 2009 Synthesis of Small Atomic Copper Clusters in Microemulsions *Langmuir* **25** 8208–8216
- [26] Link S and El-Sayed M A 2003 Optical Properties and Ultrafast Dynamics of Metallic Nanocrystals *Annu. Rev. Phys. Chem.* **54** 331-366
- [27] Eustis S and El-Sayed M A 2006 Why gold nanoparticles are more precious than pretty gold: Noble metal surface plasmon resonance and its enhancement of the radiative and nonradiative properties of nanocrystals of different shapes *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **35** 209-217
- [28] Zheng J, Zhou C, Yu M and Liu J 2012 Different sized luminescent gold nanoparticles *Nanoscale* **4** 4073–4083
- [29] Zheng J, Zhang C and Dickson R M 2004 Highly Fluorescent, Water-Soluble, Size-Tunable Gold Quantum Dots *Physical Review Letters* **93** 077402
- [30] de Heer W A 1993 The physics of simple metal clusters: experimental aspects and simple models *Rev. Mod. Phys.* **65** 611-676
- [31] Vilar-Vidal N, Blanco M C, López-Quintela M A, Rivas J and Serra C 2010 Electrochemical synthesis of very stable Photoluminiscent copper clusters *J. Phys. Chem. C* **114** 15924-15930
- [32] Chaves A S, Piotrowski M J and Da Silva J L F 2017 Evolution of the structural, energetic, and electronic properties of the 3d, 4d, and 5d transition-metal clusters (30 TM_n systems for n=2-15): a density functional theory investigation *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **19** 15484—15502
- [33] Yumura T, Kumondai M, Kuroda Y, Wakasugia T and Kobayashi H 2017 Utilizing super-atom orbital ideas to understand properties of silver clusters inside ZSM-5 zeolite *RSC Adv.* **7** 4950–4959
- [34] Copp S M, Schultz D, Swasey S, Pavlovich J, Debord M, Chiu A, Olsson K and Gwinn E 2014 Magic Numbers in DNA-Stabilized Fluorescent Silver Clusters Lead to Magic Colors *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **5** 959–963
- [35] Shayeghi A, Johnston R L and Schäfer R 2013 Evaluation of photodissociation spectroscopy as a structure elucidation tool for isolated clusters: a case study of Ag₄⁺ and Au₄⁺ *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **15** 19715-9723
- [36] Häkkinen H, Moseler M and Landman U 2002 Bonding in Cu, Ag, and Au Clusters: Relativistic Effects, Trends, and Surprises *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **89** 033401
- [37] Lee T H and Ervin K M 1994 Reactions of Copper Group Cluster Anions with Oxygen and Carbon Monoxide *J. Phys. Chem.* **98** 10023-10031
- [38] Salisbury B E, Wallace W T and Whetten R L 2000 Low-temperature activation of molecular oxygen by gold clusters: a stoichiometric process correlated to electron affinity. *Chem. Phys.* **262** 131-141
- [39] Yoon B, Häkkinen H and Landman U 2003 Interaction of O₂ with Gold Clusters: Molecular and Dissociative Adsorption *J. Phys. Chem. A* **107** 4066-4071
- [40] Boronat M and Corma A 2010 Oxygen activation on gold nanoparticles: separating the influence of particle size, particle shape and support interaction *Dalton Trans.* **39** 8538-8546
- [41] Boronat M, Leyva-Pérez A and Corma A 2014 Theoretical and Experimental Insights into the Origin of the Catalytic Activity of Subnanometric Gold

- Clusters: Attempts to Predict Reactivity with Clusters and Nanoparticles of Gold *Acc. Chem. Res.* **47** 834-844
- [42] Boronat M, Pulido A, Concepción P and Corma A 2014 Propene epoxidation with O₂ or H₂-O₂ mixtures over silver catalysts: theoretical insights into the role of the particle size *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **16** 26600- 26612
- [43] Concepción P, Boronat M, García-García S, Fernández E and Corma A 2017 Enhanced Stability of Cu Clusters of Low Atomicity against Oxidation. Effect on the Catalytic Redox Process *ACS Catalysis* **7** 3560-3568
- [44] Boronat M, López-Ausens T and Corma A 2014 Making C-C Bonds with Gold Catalysts: A Theoretical Study of the Influence of Gold Particle Size on the Dissociation of the C-X Bond in Aryl Halides *J. Phys. Chem. C* **118** 9018-9029
- [45] Gaussian 09 Revision C.01 Frisch M J, Trucks G W, Schlegel H B, Scuseria G E, Robb M A, Cheeseman J R, Scalmani G, Barone V, Mennucci B, Petersson G A, Nakatsuji H, Caricato M, Li X, Hratchian H P, Izmaylov A F, Bloino J, Zheng G, Sonnenberg J L, Hada M, Ehara M, Toyota K, Fukuda R, Hasegawa J, Ishida M, Nakajima T, Honda Y, Kitao O, Nakai H, Vreven T, Montgomery J A Jr, Peralta J E, Ogliaro F, Bearpark M, Heyd J J, Brothers E, Kudin K N, Staroverov V N, Kobayashi R, Normand J, Raghavachari K, Rendell A, Burant J C, Iyengar S S, Tomasi J, Cossi M, Rega N, Millam J M, Klene M, Knox J E, Cross J B, Bakken V, Adamo C, Jaramillo J, Gomperts R, Stratmann R E, Yazyev O, Austin A J, Cammi R, Pomelli C, Ochterski J W, Martin R L, Morokuma K, Zakrzewski V G, Voth G A, Salvador P, Dannenberg J J, Dapprich S, Daniels A D, Farkas Ö, Foresman J B, Ortiz J V, Cioslowski J, Fox D J 2009 Gaussian Inc. Wallingford CT
- [46] Reed A E, Weinstock R B and Weinhold F 1985 Natural Population Analysis *J. Chem. Phys.* **83** 735-747
- [47] Becke A D 1993 Density-functional thermochemistry. III. The role of exact exchange *J. Chem. Phys.* **98** 5648-5652
- [48] Lee C, Yang W and Parr R G 1988 Development of the Colle-Salvetti correlation-energy formula into a functional of the electron density R. G. *Phys. Rev. B* **37** 785-789
- [49] Hay P J and Wadt W R 1985 Ab Initio Effective Core Potentials for Molecular Calculations -Potentials for the Transition-Metal Atoms Sc to Hg. *J. Chem. Phys.* **82** 270-283
- [50] Hay P J and Wadt W R 1985 Ab Initio Effective Core Potentials for Molecular Calculations - Potentials for K to Au including the Outermost Core Orbitals. *J. Chem. Phys.* **82** 299-310
- [51] Wei W T, Lu Y Z, Chen W and Chen S W 2011 One-Pot Synthesis, Photoluminescence, and Electrocatalytic Properties of Sub nanometer-Sized Copper Clusters *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **133** 2060-2063
- [52] Wu Z, Lanni E, Chen W, Bier M E, Ly D and Jin R 2009 High Yield, Large Scale Synthesis of Thiolate-Protected Ag₇ Clusters *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **131**, 16672-16674
- [53] Wei C and Shaowei C 2009 Oxygen Electroreduction Catalyzed by Gold Nanoclusters: Strong Core Size Effects *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **48** 4386-4389
- [54] Yasumatsu H and Kondow T 2003 Reactive scattering of clusters and cluster ions from solid surfaces *Rep. Prog. Phys.* **66** 1783-1832

- [55] Ji Q, Zhang Y, Zhang Y and Liu Z 2015 Chemical vapour deposition of group-VIB metal dichalcogenide monolayers: engineered substrates from amorphous to single crystalline *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **44** 2587-2602
- [56] Tai G, Hu T, Zhou Y, Wang X, Kong J, Zeng T, You Y and Wang Q 2015 Synthesis of Atomically Thin Boron Films on Copper Foils *Angew. Chem.* **127** 15693-15697
- [57] Astruc D, Lu F and Aranzaes J R 2005 Nanoparticles as Recyclable Catalysts: The Frontier between Homogeneous and Heterogeneous Catalysis *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **44** 7852 – 7872
- [58] Reetz M T and Helbig W 1994 Size-Selective Synthesis of Nanostructured Transition Metal Clusters *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **116** 7401–7402
- [59] Rodríguez-Sánchez M L, Rodríguez M J, Blanco M C, Rivas J and López-Quintela M A 2005 Kinetics and Mechanism of the Formation of Ag Nanoparticles by Electrochemical Techniques: A Plasmon and Cluster Time-Resolved Spectroscopic Study *J. Phys. Chem. B* **109** 1183-1191
- [60] Gonzalez B S, Rodriguez M J, Blanco C, Rivas J, Lopez-Quintela M A and Martinho J M G 2010 One Step Synthesis of the Smallest Photoluminescent and Paramagnetic PVP-Protected Gold Atomic Clusters *Nano Lett.* **10** 4217–4221
- [61] Vilar-Vidal N, Rivas J and Lopez-Quintela M A 2012 Size dependent catalytic activity of reusable sub nanometer copper(0) clusters *ACS Catal.* **2** 1693–1697
- [62] Huseyinova S, Blanco J, Requejo F G, Ramallo-Lopez J M, Blanco M C, Buceta D and Lopez-Quintela M A 2016 Synthesis of Highly Stable Surfactant-free Cu5 Clusters in Water *J. Phys. Chem. C* **120** 15902–15908
- [63] Brust M, Walker M, Bethell D, Schiffrin D J and Whyman R 1994 Synthesis of thiol-derivatised gold nanoparticles in a two-phase Liquid–Liquid system *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.* 801–802
- [64] Brust M, Fink J, Bethell D, Schiffrin D J and Kiely C 1995 Synthesis and reactions of functionalised gold nanoparticles, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.* 1655–1656.
- [65] Wu Z K, MacDonald M A, Chen J, Zhang P and Jin R C 2011 Kinetic Control and Thermodynamic Selection in the Synthesis of Atomically Precise Gold Nanoclusters *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **133** 9670–9673
- [66] Zhu M, Lanni E, Garg N, Bier M E and Jin R 2008 Kinetically Controlled, High-Yield Synthesis of Au₂₅ Clusters *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **130** 1138–1139
- [67] Jin R, Zeng C, Zhou M and Chen Y 2016 Atomically precise colloidal metal nanoclusters and nanoparticles: fundamentals and opportunities *Chem. Rev.* **116** 10346–413
- [67] Yang H, Wang Y, Zheng N 2013 Stabilizing sub nanometer Ag(0) nanoclusters by thiolate and diphosphine ligands and their crystal structures *Nanoscale* **5** 2674–2677
- [68] Yang H, Lei J, Wu B, Wang Y, Zhou M, Xia A, Zheng L and Zheng N 2013 Crystal structure of a luminescent thiolated Ag nanocluster with an octahedral Ag₆₄+ core *Chem. Commun.* **49** 300–302
- [70] Krishna K S, Navin C V, Biswas S, Singh V, Ham K, Bovenkamp G L, Theegala C S, Miller J T, Spivey J J and Kumar C S S R 2013 Millifluidics for time-resolved mapping of the growth of gold nanostructures *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **135** 5450–6
- [71] Olivares A, Laskin J and Johnson G E 2014 Investigating the synthesis of ligated metal clusters in solution using a flow reactor and electrospray ionization mass spectrometry *J. Phys. Chem. A* **118** 8464–70

- [72] Biswas S, Miller J T, Li Y, Nandakumar K and Kumar C S S R 2012 Developing a microfluidic platform for the synthesis of ultrasmall nanoclusters; ultrasmall copper nanoclusters as a case study *Small* **8** 688–98
- [73] Navin C V, Krishna K S, Theegala C S and Kumar C S S R 2014 Lab-on-a-chip devices for gold nanoparticle synthesis and their role as a catalyst support for continuous flow catalysis *Nanotechnol. Rev.* **3** 39–63
- [74] Ran R, Sun Q, Baby T, Wibowo D, Middelberg A P J and Zhao C-X 2017 Multiphase microfluidic synthesis of micro and nanostructures for pharmaceutical applications *Chem. Eng. Sci.* **169** 78–96
- [75] Gdowski A, Johnson K, Shah S, Gryczynski I, Vishwanatha J and Ranjan A 2018 Optimization and scale up of microfluidic nanolipomer production method for preclinical and potential clinical trials *J. Nanobiotechnol.* **16** 12–22
- [69] Muetterties E L and Krause M 1983 Catalysis by Molecular Metal Clusters *J. Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.* **22** 135–148
- [70] Gates B C 1995 Supported Metal Clusters: Synthesis, Structure, and Catalysis *Chem. Rev.* **95** 511–522
- [71] Gross E, Toste F D and Somorjai G A 2015 Polymer-Encapsulated Metallic Nanoparticles as a Bridge Between Homogeneous and Heterogeneous Catalysis. *Catal Lett* **145** 126–138
- [72] Lewis L N 1993 Chemical Catalysis by Colloids and Clusters *Chem. Rev.* **93** 2693–2730
- [73] Phan N T S, Van Der Sluys M and Jones C W 2006 On the Nature of the Active Species in Palladium Catalyzed Mizoroki–Heck and Suzuki–Miyaura Couplings – Homogeneous or Heterogeneous Catalysis, A Critical Review *Adv. Synth. Catal.* **348** 609 – 679
- [74] Astruc D 2007 Palladium NP as efficient green homogeneous and heterogeneous carbon-carbon coupling pre-catalysts: a unifying view *Inorg. Chem.* **46** 1884–1894
- [75] Narayanan R, Tabor Ch and El-Sayed M A 2008 Can the observed changes in the size or shape of a colloidal nanocatalyst reveal the nanocatalysis mechanism type: homogeneous or heterogeneous? *Top. Catal.* **48** 60 – 74
- [76] Alley W M, Hamdemir I K, Johnson K A and Finke R G 2010 Ziegler-type hydrogenation catalysts made from group 8–10 transition metal precatalysts and AlR₃ cocatalysts: A critical review of the literature *J. Mol. Catal. A: Chem.* **315** 1–27
- [77] Widegren J A and Finke R G 2003 A review of the problem of distinguishing true homogeneous catalysis from soluble or other metal-particle heterogeneous catalysis under reducing conditions *J. Mol. Catal. A: Chem.* **198** 317–341
- [78] Pagliaro M, Pandarus V, Ciriminna R, Beland F and Cara P D 2012 Heterogeneous versus Homogeneous palladium catalysts for cross-coupling reactions *ChemCatChem* **4** 432–445
- [79] Hagen C M, Widegren J A, Maitlis P M and Finke R G 2005 Is It Homogeneous or Heterogeneous Catalysis? Compelling Evidence for Both Types of Catalysts Derived from [Rh(η⁵-C₅Me₅)Cl₂]₂ as a Function of Temperature and Hydrogen Pressure *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **127** 4423–4432
- [80] Bayram E, Linehan J C, Fulton J L, Roberts J A S, Szymczak N K, Smurthwaite T D, Ozkar S, Balasubramanian M and Finke R G 2011 Is It Homogeneous or Heterogeneous Catalysis Derived from [RhCp*Cl₂]₂? In Operando XAFS, Kinetic, and Crucial Kinetic Poisoning Evidence for Sub nanometer Rh₄

- Cluster-Based Benzene Hydrogenation Catalysis *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **133** 18889–18902
- [81] Shmidt F K, Nindakova L O, Shainyan B A, Saraev V V, Chipanina N N and Umanetz V A 2005 Hydrogenation catalysts formation in the system AlEt₃-Co(acac)_{2,3} *J. Mol. Catal. A: Chem.* **235** 161–172 r
- [82] Belykh L B, Titova Y Y, Umanets V A and Shmidt F K 2006 Palladium hydrogenation catalysts modified with aluminum-and phosphorus-containing compounds and with alcohols: Effect of modifiers *Russ. J. Appl. Chem.* **79** 1271–1277
- [83] Corbet J P and Mignani G 2006 Selected Patented Cross-Coupling Reaction Technologies *Chem. Rev.* **106** 2651-2710
- [84] Magano J and Dunetz J R 2011 Large-Scale Applications of Transition Metal-Catalyzed Couplings for the Synthesis of Pharmaceuticals *Chem.Rev.* **111** 2177-2250
- [85] Climent M J, Corma A and Iborra S 2012 Homogeneous and Heterogeneous catalysts for multicomponent reactions *RSC Advances* **2** 16-58
- [86] Gulevich A V, Dudnik A S, Chernyak N and Gevorgyan V 2013 Transition Metal-Mediated Synthesis of Monocyclic Aromatic Heterocycles. *Chem. Rev.* **113** 3084-3213
- [87] Heck R F 1979 Palladium-catalyzed reactions of organic halides with olefins *Acc. Chem. Res.* **12** 146-151
- [88] Miyaura N and Suzuki A 1995 Palladium-Catalyzed Cross-Coupling Reactions of Organoboron Compounds *Chem. Rev.* **95** 2457-2483
- [89] Negishi E and de Meijere A 2002 Handbook of organopalladium chemistry for organic synthesis Eds. Wiley: New York
- [90] Moreno-Mañas M and Pleixats R 2003 Formation of C-C bonds under catalysis by transition metal nanoparticles *Acc. Chem. Res.* **36** 638-643
- [91] Leyva-Pérez A, Oliver-Meseguer J, Rubio-Marqués P and Corma A 2013 Water-stabilized Three- and Four-Atom Palladium clusters as highly Active catalytic Species in Ligand-Free C-C Cross-Coupling Reactions *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **52** 11554-11559
- [92] Miyaura N 2002 Cross-Coupling Reaction of Organoboron Compounds via Base-Assisted Transmetalation to Palladium(II) Complexes *J. Organomet. Chem.* **653** 54-57
- [93] Chinchilla R and Nájera C 2007 The Sonogashira Reaction: A Booming Methodology in Synthetic Organic Chemistry *Chem. Rev.* **107** 874-922
- [94] Balanta A, Godard C and Claver C 2011 Pd nanoparticles for C-C coupling reactions *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **40** 4973-4985
- [95] Reetz M T and de Vries J G 2004 Ligand-free Heck reactions using low Pd-loading *Chem. Commun.* 1559-1563
- [96] Oliver-Meseguer J, Cabrero-Antonino J R, Dominguez I, Leyva-Perez A and Corma A 2012 Small Gold clusters formed in solution give reaction turnover numbers of 107 at room temperature *Science* **338** 1452-1455
- [97] Furukawa H, Cordova K E, O’Keeffe M, Yaghi O M 2013 The Chemistry and Applications of Metal-Organic Frameworks *Science* **341** 1230444
- [98] Fortea-Pérez F R, Mon M, Ferrando-Soria J, Boronat M, Leyva-Pérez A, Corma A, Herrera J M, Osadchii D, Gascón J, Armentano D and Pardo E 2017 The MOF-driven synthesis of supported palladium clusters with catalytic activity for carbene-mediated chemistry *Nat. Mater.* **16**, 760

- [99] Kim I S, Li Z, Zheng J, Platero-Prats A, Mavrandonakis A, Pellizzeri S, Ferrandon M, Vjunov A, Gallington L C, Webber T, Vermeulen N A, Penn R L, Getman R B, Cramer C J, Chapman K W, Camaioni D M, Fulton J L, Lercher J A, Farha O K, Hupp J T and Martinson A B F 2018 Sinter-Resistant Platinum Catalysts Supported by Metal-Organic Framework. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **57** 909-913
- [100] Corma A, Concepción P, Boronat M, Sabater M J, Navas J, Yacaman M J, Larios E, Posadas A, López-Quintela M A, Buceta D, Mendoza E, Guilera G, Mayoral A. 2013 Exceptional oxidation activity with size-controlled supported gold clusters of low atomicity *Nat. Chem.* **5** 775-781
- [101] Alves L, Ballesteros B, Boronat M, Cabrero-Antonino J R, Concepción P, Corma A, Correa-Duarte M A and Mendoza E 2011 Synthesis and Stabilization of Subnanometric Gold Oxide Nanoparticles on Multiwalled Carbon Nanotubes and Their Catalytic Activity *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **133** 10251–10261
- [102] Haruta M, Tsubota S, Kobayashi T, Kageyama H, Genet M J and Delmon B 1993 Low temperature oxidation of CO over gold supported on TiO₂, R-Fe₂O₃, and Co₃O₄ *J. Catal.* **144** 175–192
- [103] Sanchez A, Abbet S, Heiz U, Schneider W D, Häkkinen H, Barnett R N and Landman U 1999 When Gold Is Not Noble: Nanoscale Gold Catalysts *J. Phys. Chem. A* **103** 9573-9578
- [104] Yoon B, Häkkinen H, Landman U, Wörz A S, Antonietti J M, Abbet S, Judai K and Heiz U 2005 Charging Effects on Bonding and Catalyzed Oxidation of CO on Au₈ Clusters on MgO *Science* **307** 403-407
- [105] Valden M, Lai X and Goodman D W 1998 Onset of Catalytic Activity of Gold Clusters on Titania with the Appearance of Nonmetallic Properties *Science* **281** 1647-1650
- [106] Chen M S and Goodman D W 2004 The Structure of Catalytically Active Gold on Titania *Science* **306** 252-255
- [107] Chen M and Goodman D W 2006 Catalytically Active Gold: From Nanoparticles to Ultrathin Films *Acc. Chem. Res.* **39** 739-746
- [108] Matthey D, Wang J G, Wendt S, Matthiesen J, Schaub R, Lægsgaard E, Hammer B and Besenbacher F 2007 Enhanced Bonding of Gold Nanoparticles on Oxidized TiO₂(110). *Science* **315** 1692-1696
- [109] Herzing A A, Kiely C J, Carley A F, Landon P and Hutchings G J 2008 Identification of Active Gold Nanoclusters on Iron Oxide Supports for CO Oxidation *Science* **321** 1331-1335
- [110] Liu Y, Jia C J, Yamasaki J, Terasaki O and Schüth F 2010 Highly Active Iron Oxide Supported Gold Catalysts for CO Oxidation: How Small Must the Gold Nanoparticles Be? *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **49** 5771 –5775
- [111] He Q, Freakley S J, Edwards J K, Carley A F, Borisevich A Y, Mineo Y, Haruta M, Hutchings G J and Kiely C J 2016 Population and hierarchy of active species in gold iron oxide catalysts for carbon monoxide oxidation *Nature Commun.* **7** 12905
- [112] Kaden W E, Wu T, Kunkel W A and Anderson S L 2009 Electronic Structure controls reactivity of size-selected Pd clusters adsorbed on TiO₂ surfaces *Science* **326** 826-829
- [113] Lambert R M, Williams F J, Cropley R L and Palermo A 2005 Heterogeneous alkene epoxidation: past, present and future *J. Mol. Catal. A: Chem.* **228** 27-33

- [114] Nijhuis T A, Makkee M, Moulijn J A and Weckhuysen B M 2006 The Production of Propene Oxide: Catalytic Processes and Recent Developments *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* **45** 3447-3459
- [115] Pulido A, Concepción P, Boronat M and Corma A 2012 Aerobic epoxidation of propene over silver (111) and (100) facet catalysts *J. Catal.* **292** 138–147
- [116] Lei Y, Mehmood F, Lee S, Greeley J, Lee B, Seifert S, Winans R E, Elam J W, Meyer R J, Redfern P C, Teschner D, Schlögl R, Pellin M J, Curtiss L A and Vajda S. 2010 Increased Silver Activity for Direct Propylene Epoxidation via Sub nanometer Size Effects *Science* **328** 224-228
- [117] Cheng L, Yin C, Mehmood F, Liu B, Greeley J, Lee S, Lee B, Seifert S, Winans R E, Teschner D, Schlögl R, Vajda S and Curtiss L A 2014 Reaction Mechanism for Direct Propylene Epoxidation by Alumina-Supported Silver Aggregates: The Role of the Particle/Support Interface *ACS Catal.* **4** 32-39
- [118] Greiner M T, Jones T E, Johnson B E, Rocha T C R, Wang Z J, Armbrüster M, Willinger M, Knop-Gericke A and Schlögl R 2015 The oxidation of copper catalysts during ethylene epoxidation *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **17** 25073–25089
- [119] Marimuthu A, Zhang J and Linic S 2013 Tuning Selectivity in Propylene Epoxidation by Plasmon Mediated Photo-Switching of Cu Oxidation State *Science* **339** 1590–1593
- [120] Eren B, Zherebetskyy D, Patera L L, Wu C H, Bluhm H, Africh C, Wang L W, Somorjai G A and Salmeron M 2016 Activation of Cu(111) surface by decomposition into nanoclusters driven by CO adsorption *Science* **351** 475–478
- [121] Mammen N, Spanu L, Tyo E C, Yang B, Halder A, Seifert S, Pellin M J, Vajda S and Narasimhan S 2018 Reversing size-dependent trends in the oxidation of copper clusters through support effects *Eur. J. Inorg. Chem.* 16-22